

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

TO01000112-V2

**Set of 3D models and maps with results
of dynamic modelling of reservoir
behaviour and CO₂ injection scenarios
for various scenarios**

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1 INTRODUCTION

Dynamic reservoir modelling is an extremely powerful tool used to express and model the behaviour of the reservoir over time. Geological model, containing static data like seismic interpretation, well logs, cores, etc., represents a basis for building the dynamic (simulation) model. On the contrary to the static model, the simulation model contains observed data changing during the production history like pressure, fluids production, etc. The main objective of the dynamic modelling is to integrate all available data and adjust reservoir properties (if necessary) to obtain as close match of calculated with observed values as possible. Commercially available software Petrel-RE (Reservoir engineering part) and Eclipse simulator were used in dynamic modelling. Having available history matched model, prediction of future reservoir behaviour (CO₂ injection, for example) can be simulated. Fig. 1-1 illustrates the workflow of integrated approach used in the case of the Zar-3 field in the CO₂-SPICER project.

Fig. 1-1: Workflow of integrated approach.

2 DYNAMIC MODEL BUILDING

2.1 Static model import and upscaling

Static models usually contain a lot of grid blocks to be able to represent reservoir properties' changes as much as possible. Such a huge models are not suitable for running simulations causing large computational time. The geological model of the Zar-3 field contains fine grid with grid block size 10 x 10 x 1 m. This model was up-scaled vertically to 10 x 10 x 5 m (Fig. 2-1) to reduce number of grid blocks to shorten the computing time.

Fig. 2-1: Vertical upscaling.

Aiming for further reduction unneeded grid blocks laying in aquifer, out of the hydrocarbon bearing area, were made inactive and replaced with Fetkovich analytical aquifer in the simulator (Fig. 2-2).

Fig. 2-2: Reduced grid for simulation model. Violet grid blocks represent area of Fetkovich aquifer's connection.

Several versions of static model and property distributions were created in WP2 as potential basis for the dynamic model. They were imported into simulation model for testing. That iterative process was repeated several times. The most suitable permeability distribution, that gave the most realistic water and/or gas production, was selected for further history matching process in WP3.

2.2 New PVT model

A new compositional model was created (R. Berenblyum, NORCE) for the history matching and prediction period. It should be clearly stated that the only source of PVT data so far is the PVT report from 2002 prepared by INIG Krakow (INIG, 2002). The report provides a standard set of PVT experiments for the oil reservoir conducted at reservoir (52 °C) and close to standard (19 °C) conditions, however, do not address potential CO₂ interaction with reservoir fluids. An SRK equation of state was tuned to available data and both black-oil and 8-component compositional models were created. The model showed good match for relative volumes, densities and viscosities with deviation within several percent. In order to estimate compositional interaction between CO₂ and reservoir fluid several different correlations were used at reservoir temperature including uncertainty to reservoir fluid parameters (Tab. 2-1).

Tab. 2-1: Correlations used to model the interaction between CO₂ and reservoir fluids

Temperature Current	Oil density	Molecular weight of C5+ (Lasater, 1958), MW1	Molecular weight of C5+ (Mungan, 1981), MW2	MMP (Holtz, Lopez, & Breton, 2005) for MW1	MMP (Holtz, Lopez, & Breton, 2005) for MW2
°C	kg/m ³			bar	bar
52	903.2	252.4	256.7	152.7	155.7
52	911	294.0		181.6	

Judging by the correlation results. The minimum miscibility pressure is in the range of 153-182 bar, which is within the reservoir pressure range. A detailed CO₂ PVT study is needed if this reservoir will be subject to CO₂-EOR, which can become very efficient. For the current study, where the model will be used for evaluating of the pilot injection into the aquifer zone, the MMP between the CO₂ and reservoir oil was set at an average pressure of 165 bars at 52 °C.

2.3 Upscaling of geomechanical effects

The geomechanical studies in WP4 provided results that has been used in the simulation model. By analysing reservoir rock samples, using the “Coreval 700” device at VSB Ostrava, the relation between pore volume, permeability and hydrostatic stress was measured. Pore volume and transmissibility multipliers were derived from the measurements (Fig. 2-3) and used as an input into ROCKTAB keyword in Eclipse simulator.

Fig. 2-3: Pore volume multiplier (a) and transmissibility multiplier displaying the relation between pore volume, permeability and of pore pressure. The average relation from selected samples shown as solid line.

The geomechanical strength of reservoir samples were determined in the tensile regime by Brazilian tests, in the shear strength by Unconfined compressive strength and triaxial tests (Nermoen, Porzer, Klempa, & Sancer, 2024), and the stress-state at which pre-existing fractures occur is shown in *qp*-space in Fig. 2-4. Given uncertainty in stress, Biot coefficient, thermal-elastic coupling coefficient and pore pressure, the initial stresses and the shifted stress-configuration are displayed as green and grey areas in Fig. 2-4 using Monte Carlo techniques (Nermoen, Shchipanov, Porzer, & Sancer, 2024). This enables the calculation of the pore pressure and reservoir temperature at which 1% of the simulated cases were geomechanically unstable Fig. 2-5. Here, the pressure at which re-opening of pre-existing fractures, generate new tensile fractures and shear failure can be determined for each temperature.

Fig. 2-5: The pore pressure at which 1% of the instances in the Monte Carlo simulation as function of temperature for three failure modes. At 15°C, this corresponds to critical pressures of 224, 267 and 285 bars, respectively. These critical pressures were used in the dynamic permeability exceeding the elastic limit (transmissibility multiplier).

As the COREVAL 700 tool enable a physical relation between pore pressure, pore volume and permeability this is only valid in the elastic regime for intact rocks. When the pore pressure exceeds the least tectonic stress (224 bars), however, fractures will re-open, and if pore pressure exceeds the least tectonic stress plus the tensile strength (267 bars) new fractures will develop. This will lead to a significantly increase the permeability as displayed in Fig. 2-6, where the estimated permeability and porosity multiplier is plotted, while calculated permeability multiplier is calculated as an exponential function of pressure.

Fig. 2-6: Porosity and permeability (without fracture opening) multipliers for the elastic regime (from Fig. 2-3). As pore pressure exceed the threshold as shown in Figure 6, the permeability multiplier for re-opening of existing fractures (titled as fracture opening) is included.

The critical pressures above rely on certainty of the input geomechanical data (i.e. the actual value and likely range), the risk appetite of the operator reflected in the probability of failure (here 1%), and temperature.

One of several possible reservoir development scenarios that is being evaluated, is a gas cap depletion. So another important result from geochemical experiments was answering the question whether it is possible to deplete gas from the gas cap and deplete gas and dramatically reduce the reservoir pressure. The consequence of a depletion down to 0 MPa can be seen as the shift to the grey area in Fig. 2-7. As can be seen, the stress state at depletion is within the obtained failure envelope from the geomechanical experiments that has been executed. As such, based on the geomechanical loading/unloading experiments, there seem to be no pressure depletion limit as the geomechanical compaction strength (grey dashed line) is to the right of the grey zone, i.e., as the cores tested seemed to withstand the effective stress increase related to drawdown to 0 MPa. The cloud of data is well within the safe operation window.

Fig. 2-7: Failure envelope of the reservoir samples in the Zar-3 field obtained from geomechanical strength tests.

2.4 Geochemistry effects

Several effects may significantly affect the CO₂ injectivity into any given reservoir in addition to geomechanical effects discussed above, among geochemistry effects two may have strong impact on pilot CO₂ injection:

- Hydrate formation.
- Salt precipitation due to water drying out.

Hydrate formation is a function of temperature, pressure, and salinity. The hydrates form in higher pressure, lower temperature, and lower salinity environment. For expected reservoir pressures during pilot injection, relatively low salinity a CO₂ bottom hole temperature of around 15 degrees should prevent hydrate formation. With the expected low-rate injection in the pilot phase pre-heating the CO₂ at the surface and geothermal heating as it travels down the well seem to provide a safe operational regime.

Potential salt precipitation seems to be the major risk factor for well infectivity at pilot CO₂ injection. When CO₂ is injected to reservoirs, all injected CO₂ will pass the near well region. It is then important that the risks for formation damages are low, e. g. by salt precipitation, hydrate formation, fines migration, bacteria activity, temperature and pressure cycling. Injection of dry CO₂ phase will give evaporation of water in water-bearing formations. The concentration of ions in the water phase will then gradually increase until max solubility is reached, and salt precipitation will then occur. The potential of salt precipitation depends on several parameters, e. g. water-phase composition, residual water saturation, flow rate, pressure and temperature. The risk for permeability reduction by salt precipitation depends on the location of the precipitate in the pore-space and thereby on rock properties, fluid compositions and local flow regimes.

Formation damage by salt precipitation includes three main mechanisms: Salt precipitation, migration of salt crystals and accumulation of crystals at pore throats. All these mechanisms should be included in modelling/simulations of the process. It has been reported that modelling of vaporization by equilibrium cannot describe core flooding experiments in a good way.

Injection of CO₂ into aquifers of high porosity and permeability rock will give longer migration due to the injection pressure. A large dry-out can be formed in the near well regions of these reservoirs. The CO₂-water capillary pressure in these zones is low, and the effect of capillary pressure on salt is therefore low. Salt precipitation is often not causing much formation damage in these reservoirs. For rocks with low porosity and permeability, the CO₂-water capillary pressure is high and salt precipitation becomes more important. The irreducible water saturation is much higher and the smaller pore throats is easier to block by salt precipitation. The low porosity and permeability give more back flow of brine to the well-bore due to the high CO₂-water capillary pressure. This causes more salt precipitation to occur in the near well region. Blockage of pore throats and low CO₂ injectivity can occur even though the salinity is not very high.

The extension of the dry-out / salt precipitation zone depends on parameters as brine compositions, rock properties, flow regimes and time. Extension of the dry-out zone to be large in high porosity and permeability formations with not much formation damage, but less extension in low porosity and permeability formations with larger formation damage. The dry-out zone can reach tens of meters from the injector.

A mechanistic simulation was carried out to study salt precipitation near the wellbore. The reservoir salinity is 12 200 mg/l with chloride and a bit over 26 000 mg/l if all ions are taken together. The near wellbore reservoir simulation was used to estimate the scale of salt precipitation in this case (assuming 25% residual water saturation, 60 m pay depth and 30 mD permeability). Maximum salt precipitation reached 10% in the cell containing the well itself. After approximately half a year of injection the salt precipitation stopped affecting in total only around 0.6 cm around the wellbore. This study in combination with the literature referenced above were used as a reference for suggesting salt precipitation potential for the field in focus. The ranges for potential permeability reduction and the size of the near wellbore area affected by the salt precipitation were then assessed as: 10 - 80% and 0.5 - 5 m correspondingly. These range were further converted into well skin factor and applied in the sensitivity studies of the CO₂ injection scenarios.

3 HISTORY MATCH

One of the main tasks during history matching process was to perform a conditioning of the permeability distribution to match the dynamic data analysis. The permeability distribution as obtained from the geomodel represented initial input into dynamic model. The permeability map resulting from the geomodel is illustrated in Fig. 3-1.

Fig. 3-1: Permeability from geomodel.

As a first step permeability from geomodel had to be compared and matched to the permeability from the pressure transient analysis (PTA) for individual wells. Permeability value obtained from the PTA represents one value for the individual well's region of investigation and not only for the well's trajectory. So the regions around the individual wells were extracted from the whole grid and average permeability of the region was compared with the value from the PTA. A permeability multiplier for the well's region was calculated by dividing the value from the PTA by the value from the geomodel. The process is illustrated on the example of ZA3 well: permeability of 150 mD was determined from the PTA within the radius of investigation equal to 150 m. Grid blocks laying in that radius around the ZA3 well were extracted from the whole grid by using Well region method in the Geometrical modelling functionality in Petrel.

Mean permeability value in the region in the geomodel was 61 mD. Permeability multiplier approx. equal to 2.5 for the ZA3 well was calculated by dividing PTA value with the geomodel value ($150 : 61 = 2.5$).

Values of the permeability multipliers for all wells where PTA results are available are displayed in Tab. 3-1. Quite high values of multipliers are evident in some wells,

which can be explained by the fact that logs, the basic source for the geomodel, are not able to contain relatively thin features like fractures that can cause quite high permeabilities.

Tab. 3-1: Values of the permeability multipliers for all wells where PTA results are available are displayed in the table below

Well	Perm PTA (mD)	Perm Geomodel (mD)	Multiplier
ZA3	150	61	2.5
ZA4A	350	25	14
ZA5H	550	41	13.4
ZA7	55	5.7	9.65
ZA9AH	90	21	4.3

Multipliers' values were inter/extrapolated among individual wells in 3D using Moving average method in Petrophysical modelling in Petrel. Resulting map of the multiplier is illustrated in Fig. 3-2.

Fig. 3-2: Map of permeability multiplier.

Permeability obtained from the geomodel was then multiplied with the multiplier in 3D and the consequent permeability was checked in an Eclipse runs. The main emphasis was on comparing the average permeability values in the individual wells' regions with the values obtained from PTA. As the multipliers' values could be assigned just for the grid blocks that are cut with the wells' trajectories but not for the whole regions of investigation, it was obvious that average permeability values in the wells' regions will not perfectly match the PTA values. So additional multipliers had to be applied to condition the permeability to the PTA values in individual wells' regions. Having enough static and dynamic pressure measurements integrated into the simulation model, the next step consisted of obtaining pressure drawdowns' match between the calculated bottomhole pressures by the simulator and observed data. Applying additional multipliers in some wells was inevitable because, even after previous permeability adjustment, higher pressure drawdowns were still calculated by the simulator. That additional permeability increase did cause good pressure drawdowns match (see example of the ZA3 well in Fig. 3-3) but simultaneously higher permeabilities were obtained in some wells' regions compare to the PTA values. The only way how to get acceptable match in the wells' regions and at the same time keep the already properly matched drawdowns' values was to decrease the permeability among some wells where there is no control. Resulting permeability served as an initial 3D input into the simulation run containing the whole production history. Final small permeability changes had to be carried out to match observed gas – oil ratios and water cuts in individual producers. The final permeability map resulting from the history match process is illustrated in Fig. 3-4.

Fig. 3-3: Pressure drawdown's match in the ZA3 well.

Fig. 3-4: Permeability map resulting from history match.

ZA3 well, a discovery well, was the first producer in the Zar-3 field. Having opened quite long interval in the oil zone, the gas from the gas cap reached topmost part of the open hole, which caused increasing gas – oil ratio (GOR) to the level that the production from the well was terminated. Since 2006 the well was used as an observation one allowing occasional measurements of static bottom hole pressure (BHP). The pressure measurements were extremely useful during the history match process allowing determine initial hydrocarbons' volumes and aquifer size. The match of the observed pressure measurements (circles) and the BHP calculated by the simulator (line) is displayed in Fig. 3-5.

Fig. 3-5: Bottom hole pressure match in the ZA3 well.

Several parameters influence the pressure trend during the production history: volume of free gas in the gas cap, volume of solution gas in the oil, volume of oil in the oil zone, volume of water in the aquifer, connectivity throughout the reservoir, presence of communication barriers, etc. Static pressures measured in the ZA3 well indicate important pressure support from the aquifer. BHP declined from approx. 173 to 124 bars after more than 22 years of production, when approx. 470 thousand cubic meters of oil, 52 mil. cubic meters of gas, and 287 thousand cubic meters of water have been produced. If there was weak or no aquifer support, the pressure decline would be much higher.

Excellent pressure match was obtained using the following reservoir volumes:

- Gas cap (free gas) = 110 mil. m³
- Solution gas = 70 mil. m³
- Oil = 1.1 mil. m³
- Water:
 - Active grid blocks = 3.6 mil. m³
 - Numerical aquifer = 30 mil. m³

In the end of this work package is essence a physics based model capable of capturing the essential observations as described above. Then we can move over to describe the simulations that is to be performed.

4 SIMULATION OF CO₂ PILOT INJECTION

Solvent model, a four-component extension of the ECLIPSE black-oil model, was used allowing introducing CO₂ properties as the 4th reservoir fluid (apart from gas, oil, and water). Two scenarios of CO₂ pilot injection were simulated: CO₂ injection into ZA3 well after gas cap depletion and CO₂ injection into ZA7 well before the gas cap depletion. Legislation allows to cumulatively inject maximum 100 thousand tons of CO₂ during the pilot injection. So, focusing on the pilot itself, not on the full field application, the 2nd scenario could be implemented in the practise.

4.1 CO₂ pilot injection after gas cap depletion

It was simulated that the gas from the gas cap was produced only by ZA3 well. This well is the most suitable for the gas cap depletion due to its top-most position in the gas saturated structure. The currently open well production interval lies in the oil zone, so this was squeezed in the model and the top-most reservoir interval was opened for gas production. The gas cap depletion was terminated before water production started in the simulator due to the surface facility treating gas production is not adapted to excessive water production. The same interval as used for the gas production was then also used for the CO₂ injection in later phase of the simulation. CO₂ was simulated to be injected into the former gas zone.

Simulation shows that the field pressure declines up to 48 bars during the gas cap depletion and increases up to 80 bars during the pilot CO₂ injection, which is illustrated in Fig. 4-1.

Fig. 4-1: Field pressure during production history, gas cap depletion and pilot CO₂ injection.

As gas from the gas cap is being produced, formation water moves to upper structural position so only thin gas and oil saturated zones remain in the structure, which is obvious from Fig. 4-2.

Fig. 4-2: Saturation after gas cap depletion.

CO₂ was simulated to be injected in the upper most interval of the ZA3 well. Injection of 120 tons of CO₂ per day and 70 thousand tons cumulatively during the pilot injection period within less than two years was simulated. Even at declined reservoir pressure after the gas cap depletion, the injected CO₂ has higher density than natural gas so the injected CO₂ is accumulated predominantly around the injector and below the gas saturated zone as can be seen in Fig. 4-3.

Fig. 4-3: CO₂ saturation at the end of the injection into ZA3 well.

4.2 CO₂ pilot injection before gas cap depletion

One of the main advantages of the commencing the CO₂ injection before the gas cap depletion is that the reservoir pressure remains sufficiently high to reduce the Joule–Thomson cooling effect. Another benefit here is CO₂ injected and flowing inside the reservoir in the supercritical phase .

The ZA7 well was chosen as the CO₂ injector profiting from the fact that the well is currently being used for produced water injection. The well was recently re-completed with fiberglass tubing, which makes it perfect candidate for the CO₂ injection, without significant additional costs for converting it into CO₂ injector. The nearby ZA3 well is currently used as an observation well and therefore may be further used for reservoir monitoring during the pilot CO₂ injection. The well ZA7 penetrates aquifer part of the field and CO₂ is therefore injected into the water zone.

In the simulation, the injection of 120 tons of CO₂ per day and 70 thousand tons cumulatively during the pilot injection period within less than two years (i.e. 583 days) was simulated.

Similar increase in average field pressure is obvious from Fig. 4-4. The field pressure declined from initial 174 to 121 bars during the primary production. Simulation result indicates increase by 9 bars to 130 bars during the pilot injection.

Fig. 4-4: Field pressure during production history and pilot CO₂ injection.

Injected CO₂ is assumed to have lower density than formation water and oil but higher than gas in the gas cap at the reservoir pressure and temperature during the pilot. Consequently, the injected CO₂ is supposed to accumulate around the ZA7 injection well, migrate through the structure and segregate by gravity at the top of oil zone and bottom of the gas cap as illustrated in Fig. 4-5.

Fig. 4-5: CO₂ saturation at the end of pilot injection into ZA7 well.

Additional simulations were carried out to quantify uncertainty associated with possible salt precipitation in the main pilot injection scenario. Salt precipitation may cause permeability reduction in the near wellbore area of a certain radius, which can be modelled by increasing skin value in injection well. The sensitivity was run for the permeability reduced by 10 and 80% and the radius of the near wellbore area with the reduced permeability varying from 0.5 to 5 m. These ranges resulted in the skin values of 0.21 (10%, 0.5 meters, ignored further since is very close to zero), 0.46 (10%, 5 meters), 7.43 (80%, 0.5 meters), and 16.64 (80%, 5 meters). The pilot simulation described above assumed zero skin and was used as the reference case for the skin sensitivity. The skin sensitivity of the pilot injection scenario is shown in Fig. 4-6 and demonstrates about 6 bar of additional pressure drop due to skin in the most risky scenario with skin of 16.64. So presence of skin may double the BHP build-up during the pilot injection (achieving 148 bar), although the BHP remains far from the natural fracture opening pressure (224 bar).

Fig. 4-6: Injection pressure increase due to salt precipitation during Pilot injection.

As a final step, potential CO₂ injection capacity of the reservoir assuming injection at the maximum pressure of 267 bar corresponding to the induced fracturing pressure following the geomechanical evaluations for the temperature of 15 °C (Fig. 2-5) was estimated. Here, since the well BHP may overcome the fracture opening pressure of 224 bar, effect of fracture opening was studied applying two permeability multipliers: accounting and not accounting for the fracture opening (Fig. 2-6). In addition, the well skin sensitivity (due to the salt precipitation) was studied similarly to the simulations of the pilot injection above.

The simulation results Fig. 4-7(a) showed that CO₂ injection rate is significantly higher for the cases of low or no skin (0 and 0.46), since reservoir pressure in the near wellbore area is close to BHP (267 bar), which is much higher than the fracture opening pressure. This causes high pressure in the near wellbore area and opening the natural fractures. In the cases with high skin (7.43 and 16.64) high well-reservoir pressure drop is established with the pressure in the near wellbore area exceeding the fracture opening pressure only after some period of time (about half-year after the injection start for the case of skin of 7.43). This is an interesting effect of interplaying between fracture opening and skin effects that should be accounted for in further evaluations of the large-scale injection scenarios. The average reservoir pressure dynamics for the sensitivity runs is illustrated in Fig. 4-7(b). The total CO₂ storage capacity in all the scenarios with the injection at induced fracturing pressure may be estimated as around 500 million m³ or around 900 thousand tons Fig. 4-7(c).

5 CONCLUSION

The main goals of dynamic modelling were create history matched full-field model of planned storage site and simulate different options of CO₂ injection accounting for most important effects related to CO₂ storage in fractured carbonate reservoir.

Dynamic model was built on static model obtained from WP2. Choosing the most representative static model requested close and extensive cooperation with geologists. The most suitable geological model, that gave the most realistic water and/or gas production, was selected for further history matching process.

Geomechanical assessments were upscaled into the simulation model contributing to (i) assembling, history matching and forecasting CO₂ injection using the reservoir model via applying pressure-sensitive reservoir properties in the reservoir simulations as well as (ii) assembling safe injection envelope for conditioning CO₂ injection scenarios.

Geochemistry effects (potential salt precipitation) on CO₂ injection simulations and the performance of the CO₂ injection scenarios had been upscaled into the dynamic model.

First step of history match process consisted of conditioning permeability distribution from geological model to the dynamic data analysis. The resulted permeability distribution was then tested in reproducing the field production history. Matching the well pressure history and well pressure drops were paid the main attention. Further fine tuning of the multipliers for some wells was carried out to match the well measurements. Achieving acceptable history matching results, the reservoir model was further used for simulation of the pilot CO₂ injection scenarios.

Solvent model, a four-component extension of the ECLIPSE black-oil model, was used allowing introducing CO₂ properties as the 4th reservoir fluid (apart from gas, oil, and water). Two scenarios of CO₂ pilot injection were simulated: CO₂ injection into ZA3 well after gas cap depletion and CO₂ injection into ZA7 well before the gas cap depletion. Injecting 120 tons CO₂ per day within less than two years (cumulatively 70 thousand tons) was assumed in both scenarios. The second scenario is more preferable due to advantage that the reservoir pressure remains sufficiently high to reduce the Joule–Thomson cooling effect. Another benefit is CO₂ injected and flowing inside the reservoir will be in the supercritical phase.

Simulations show that the pilot CO₂ injection at relatively low injection rates is feasible even assuming possible salt precipitation due to bottom hole pressure build-up during the pilot injection remains far from the natural fracture opening pressure.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Set of 3D, 2D model views, maps

Figure 1: 3D view of initial saturation before starting production (red – gas, green – oil, blue – water)

Figure 2: X-Section in 3D view of initial saturation before starting production

Figure 3: 3D view of saturation at the end of history match

Figure 4: X-Section in 3D view (ZA3-ZA4A) of saturation at the end of history match

Figure 5: X-Section in 3D view (ZA7) of saturation at the end of history match

Figure 6: 3D view of saturation at the end of pilot CO₂ injection into ZA7 well

Figure 7: X-Section in 3D view of CO₂ saturation at the end of pilot CO₂ injection into ZA7 well

Figure 8: Map of CO₂ saturation at the end of pilot CO₂ injection into ZA7 well

Figure 9: 3D view of saturation after gas cap depletion

Figure 10: X-Section in 3D view of saturation after gas cap depletion

Figure 11: 3D view of saturation at the end of pilot CO₂ injection into ZA3 well

Figure 12: X-Section in 3D view of CO₂ saturation at the end of pilot CO₂ injection into ZA3 well

Figure 13: Map of CO₂ saturation at the end of pilot CO₂ injection into ZA3 well

Figure 1: 3D view of initial saturation before starting production (red – gas, green – oil, blue – water).

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Figure 4: X-Section in 3D view (ZA3-ZA4A) of saturation at the end of history match.

Figure 5: X-Section in 3D view (ZA7) of saturation at the end of history match.

Figure 6: 3D view of saturation at the end of pilot CO₂ injection into ZA7 well.

Figure 7: X-Section in 3D view of CO₂ saturation at the end of pilot CO₂ injection into ZA7 well.

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co2-spicer.geology.cz.

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